

The Stability Effect of Pipe Shoes on Steel Beams

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ABSTRACT

Section 6.3.5.2 of Eurocode EN 1993-1-1 provides guidance to ensure an effective lateral and torsional restraint to lateral forces and torsion induced by local plastic deformation of steel beams. The typical restraints are a stiff torsional restraint or a lateral and torsional restraint by a slab to the compression flange.

The focus of this paper is on the industrial structures such as pipe racks, with primary pipe supporting function. The vertical load from pipes is generally applied by means of pipe shoes which are welded to the pipe and resting at the top flange of the steel beam.

This paper addresses the stabilizing effect of the load application on the lateral torsional buckling of steel beams considering that the pipe remains aligned with (limited) horizontal movements in the longitudinal and transverse direction of the pipes, these lateral movements are mainly due to thermal expansion.

This paper assesses the partial torsional restraint provided by the pipe shoe to the top flange of the steel beam. The assessment is done by simulating this effect using a FE analysis considering a simple supporting beam with a concentrated load applied at the midspan.

This paper contributes by providing conservative guidance on the effective unbraced length of the top flange for flexural design of steel beams supporting pipes.

Keywords: Lateral Torsional Buckling, LTB, Pipe shoe, Steel Design

1 INTRODUCTION

Pipe shoes are the interface between the pipe and its support, they elevate the piping from beams or other surfaces, they protect process systems in several ways: i) they can stop pipes from rubbing against dissimilar metals; ii) as pipes move, pipe shoes keep insulation from grinding against objects or rupturing. In the same way, they should minimize the movement and wear that comes with heat transfer. Fig. 1 shows a pipe with its shoe.

Fig. 1. Pipe with a pipe shoe

In practice, steel pipe shoes are made with built up T-sections that are welded to pipes and rest on top of supporting steel beams. The interaction between pipes shoes and the supporting beams may be classified whether as (1) directional anchors, restraining transverse and longitudinal movement of the pipes, (2) guides, restraining transverse movement of the pipes, (3) hold down supports, restraining vertical movement of the pipes up and down, (4) simple resting supports, mainly providing vertical support, these simple resting supports are not connected to the beams, thus allowing thermal expansion of the pipes, the thermal forces (or part of it) are transferred to the beams by means of friction.

The scope of this study focusses on the interaction of the simple resting pipe shoes assuming the pipe shoe remains horizontal, the beams provide only vertical support for the gravity loads. At the ultimate design when the beam start experiencing lateral torsional buckling it is then assumed that the pipe slightly moves following the lateral torsional displacement of the top flange of the beam.

In practice, a beam may support multiple pipes resting on top of it, so it would have a distributed load. However, this study focussed the case of one concentrated load applied at the midspan for two main reasons (1) simplicity, and (2) to conservatively consider the stabilizing effect of the load application to only one location.

Section 6.3.5 of EN 1993-1-1 considers the cases where beams have enough lateral restraints to prevent failure on stability mode so the beams can generate the full plastic capacity. The cases that are considered to be effective restraints are (1) a stiff torsional restraint to the cross-section preventing the lateral displacement of the compression flange relative to the tension flange, and (2) the other case is a beam where the compression flange is in contact with a floor slab providing lateral and torsional restraint to the compression flange. These cases are shown in Fig 6.5 and Fig 6.6 of EN 1993-1-1 respectively.

Figure 6.5: Typical stiff torsional restraint

1 compression flange

Figure 6.6: Typical lateral and torsional restraint by a slab to the compression flange

Fig. 2. Cases of lateral restraint considers in EN 1993-1-1

This paper focusses on the case of partial lateral and torsional restraint provided by the load application which remain horizontal such that when the beam try to rotate by lateral torsional buckling the load application would experience a natural shift towards the tip of the top flange causing a stabilizing effect.

Fig. 3. a) Initial condition; b) Shift of the load application towards the tip of the top flange causing a stabilizing effect

1.1 Research Objectives

The main objective of this research is to determine the stabilizing effect of the verticality of the load application on the lateral torsional buckling resistance of a steel beam when a horizontal pipe shoe rests on its top flange. It is also intended to propose design rules to assess flexural resistance considering whether a reduction of the unbraced length of the top flange is an adequate approximation to assess the stabilizing effect of the load application.

Fig. 4. Point 1 shows the original non-loaded situation. Point 2 shows the theoretical results with a failure in lateral torsional buckling. Point 3 shows the stabilizing effect of the pipe shoe.

1.2 Research Methodology

For this research, finite element models were developed using 2D members to simulate the cross section of the beam. A total of 8 different steel cross-sections (4 hot-rolled I-sections and 4 hot-rolled H-sections) with a beam length of 6 meters were considered. The models were first validated against the expected behaviour of steel beams under normal support conditions by comparing its results to analytical values obtained using the Eurocode provisions.

Once the models are validated, the models are used to perform linear and nonlinear analysis to determine the maximum vertical load that the beams can resist. From those values, the buckling moment resistance and the effective reduction factor are solved.

2 NUMERICAL STUDY

This section summarizes the numerical study performed in this paper. For this firstly the modelling assumptions are presented followed by the numerical parametric study.

The models consider geometrical and material non-linear analysis with imperfections (GMNIA). The material non-linearity assumes yielding without the plastic hardening effects.

2.1 Modelling of Cross Sections

The numerical model was built using software ABAQUS/CAE. The cross-sections were modelled using shell elements with reduced integration S4R. In total eight cross sections were used in this study, see Table 1.

The connectivity of members, which dictates the flow of forces, are defined by what is called a ‘system line’. Since 2D shell and plate elements are only initially defined as lines connecting three or more nodes, the thicknesses are dictated by the chosen position of the system line.

To simulate a steel beam cross-section, shells with four nodes each were connected along their system lines to form the flanges and the webs. For simplicity the root between the web and the flanges has been neglected in the FEM model. Likewise, the modified cross section properties were used to obtain the cross-section properties and the resistance capacity following the rules of the Eurocode.

A modelled IPE 160 beam and the typical scheme used for the system lines in this paper can be seen in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Front view of the IPE 160 FEM Model (a) and Typical system lines of modelled I-beams with system-generated meshing along the length of the beam (b).

2.2 Material grade

This study uses steel grade S235. For the nonlinear analysis, linear elastic perfectly plastic material with a yield stress of 235MPa was considered. The post-yielding hardening effect has been neglected.

2.3 Modelling of initial imperfections

The initial imperfection was adopted with the shape of the first global buckling mode scaled with equivalent geometric imperfection according to Eurocode 3.

As shown in Table 1, the 8x cross-sections considered had a height – width (h/b) ratios less than or equal to 2.0, therefore for LTB resistance all cross-sections corresponded to the buckling curve “a”. This results in an initial local bow imperfection of L/250 for plastic analysis.

Table 1. Cross sections considered [mm] and the recommended buckling curve and bow imperfections.

section	h	b	h/b	Buckling curve	Bow Imperfection for Plastic Analysis e_0/L
IPE 120	120	64	1.88	a	1/250
IPE 160	160	82	1.95	a	
IPE 200	200	100	2.00	a	
IPE 240	240	120	2.00	a	
HEA 120	114	120	0.95	a	
HEA 160	152	160	0.95	a	
HEA 200	190	200	0.95	a	
HEA 240	230	240	0.96	a	

Fig. 6. Typical buckling mode considering the stabilizing effect of the load application.

2.4 Modelling of the Pipe Shoe

The geometry of pipe shoes has been considered as a built-up T-section made of plates welded together. The pipe shoe was modeled using 2 shell elements: one for the web and one for the flange. The dimensions and degrees of freedom of the pipe shoe are shown in Fig. 7.

To simulate the pipe shoe in the FEM model, the top part of the web which is normally welded to a pipe is considered rigid in bending and free to move in the longitudinal and vertical direction. For the FEM model it is considered with 2 degrees of freedom.

Fig.7. Pipe shoe dimensions and degrees of freedom

The pipe shoe is placed on the top flange of the beams. It is interacting with the beam using General contact in Abaqus using friction coefficient of 0.2.

2.5 Loading Conditions

This research considers only the vertical force applied via the pipe shoe to the supporting steel beam. It is considered that the pipe allows for the lateral torsional deformation of the top flange, so moving downwards and longitudinally along with the top flange on the beam however remaining in the horizontal position.

The objective of the FEM analysis is to achieve the ultimate capacity of the beam on lateral torsional buckling mode considering the stabilizing effect of the pipe shoe but avoiding other failure mechanisms e.g. local web buckling, therefore the FEM analysis considers stiffeners on the beam at the load application such that lateral torsional buckling failure mechanism is ensured.

For the FEM analysis, the vertical load is applied on top of the pipe shoe as a uniformly distributed load simulating the loads transfer by a real pipe. This load is then transferred from the pipe shoe to the contact surface of the top flange.

Fig. 8. Loading on the FEM model with stiffeners on the beam to avoid local web buckling.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are presented in Fig. 9, where point 1 indicates the original beam capacity for a simple supported beam according the rules of the Eurocode with a concentrated load applied at the top of the cross-section at the midspan of the beam, then point 2 represents the capacity increase due to the stabilizing effect of the load application, and point 3 represents the reduction of the non-dimensional slenderness considering 50% as the effective length factor (k_z) on the calculation of the critical moment M_{cr} .

Fig. 9. Results showing (1) the initial beam capacity, (2) the capacity increase considering the stabilizing effect of the pipe shoe, (3) the proposed conservative approach considering 50% as effective length factor ($k_z = 0.5$).

The choice of using the reduction of the effective length (k_z) in order to obtain the critical moment and then the corresponding non-dimensional slenderness is basically for simplicity. In practice these beams are normally calculated using a 1D members and a linear analysis method, so in order to capitalize the advantages of the stabilizing effect of the load application, a simple and conservative method can be considered as a fit-for-purpose solution.

Fig. 9 shows that all points where the effective length factor have been reduced to 50% remains above the buckling curve, this means that there is still a level of conservatism within the approach.

Fig. 10 shows a typical buckling mode accounting for the stabilizing effect of the horizontality of the load application such as pipe shoes.

A preliminary conclusion may be: To account for the stabilizing effect of the horizontality of the load application such as pipe shoes, it is safe to consider an effective length factor k_z equal to 0.5 to calculate the resistance of simple supported beams with a concentrated load applied at midspan.

Fig. 10. Results using the buckling mode which corresponds to full restraint by the pipe shoe.

3.1 Recommendations for future research

Since this study considers only a few numbers of cases, it is recommended to increase the number of cases using different cross-sections and lengths. Similarly, it is recommended to extend the study for the cases of uniform distributed load.

This study focussed only on simple supported beams, then another recommendation is to extend the analysis to other boundary conditions such as moment connections.

Another recommendation is to validate the FE analysis with a physical test, this way it can be ensured the correctness of the numerical model and derived more robust conclusions.

In practice the pipes are subject to thermal expansion causing a friction load applied at the point of contact with the pipe shoes. For a small number of pipes it is usually use a full steel-to-steel friction coefficient of 30% applicable for cases of a concentrated load, however when the number of pipes increases, then the likelihood that all pipes are moving in the same direction is smaller, therefore it is usually applied an unbalance friction force with an average friction coefficient of 10% which is applicable for cases of uniform distributed load.

The recommendations for future research are summarized below:

1. Increase the number of cases with different cross-sections and lengths.
2. Extend the study using uniform distributed loads.
3. Extend the study to other boundary conditions such as moment connections.
4. Validate the FE analysis with physical tests.
5. Extend the study to load combinations, for concentrated load apply 30% of friction, and for uniform distributed load and unbalanced friction of 10% may be used.